

NORMAL HEIGHT DETERMINATION FROM DIFFERENT METHODOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT – The determination of normal height is essential for scientific and engineering applications, and it is intrinsically linked to the Earth's gravity potential. This study compares two methodologies for computing normal heights following the International Height Reference System (IHR) conventions. The first strategy estimates gravity potential via a geoid model derived from Least Squares Collocation (LSC) with gridded data; the second determines the disturbing potential through Numerical Integration (NI) using a modified Hotine integral and non-gridded data. A total of 112 benchmarks from the High Precision Altimetric Network (RAAP) in the Brazilian states of São Paulo and Minas Gerais were used for comparison. Results show a mean difference of -0.05 m between the LSC and NI methods and 0.60 m when compared with the official RAAP values. The findings suggest that both methods are consistent, particularly in regions with smooth gravity disturbance patterns, although discrepancies increase in areas with poor gravity data coverage. These outcomes support the applicability of the proposed methods in heterogeneous geodetic infrastructures, especially in developing countries.

RESUMO – A determinação da altitude normal é essencial para aplicações científicas e de engenharia, e está intrinsecamente ligada ao potencial gravidade da Terra. Este estudo compara duas metodologias para calcular altitudes normais seguindo as convenções do Sistema Internacional de Referência de Altitude (*International Height Reference System* - IHR). A primeira estratégia estima o potencial de gravidade por meio de um modelo geoidal derivado da Colocação por Mínimos Quadrados (*Least Squares Collocation* - LSC) com dados em grade; a segunda determina o potencial perturbador por meio da Integração Numérica (NI) usando uma integral de Hotine modificada e dados não gradeados. Um total de 112 referências de nível da Rede Altimétrica de Alta Precisão (RAAP) nos estados brasileiros de São Paulo e Minas Gerais foram usados para comparação. Os resultados mostram uma diferença média de -0,05 m entre os métodos LSC e NI e 0,60 m quando comparados com os valores de altitude da RAAP. Os resultados sugerem que ambos os métodos são consistentes, particularmente em regiões com padrões suaves de distúrbio de gravidade, embora as discrepâncias aumentem em áreas com baixa cobertura de dados terrestres de gravidade. Esses resultados corroboram a aplicabilidade dos métodos propostos em infraestruturas geodésicas heterogêneas, especialmente em países em desenvolvimento.

1 INTRODUCTION

Determining physical height and anomalous quantities, such as geoid undulation, height anomaly, and disturbing potential, depends on the solution to the Geodetic Boundary Value Problem (GBVP). The geoid and quasi-geoid models

are traditionally computed by solving the GBVP, using gravity anomalies in the scalar-free problem or gravity disturbances with the fixed problem (SÁNCHEZ et al., 2021). Its consistency is evaluated based on GNSS measurements and the physical heights derived from the leveling network.

With the advent of the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), the use of gravity disturbances as input offers benefits beyond gravity anomalies, as they are independent of the gravity reduction procedures to the geoid. Additionally, they are effortlessly determined and can be a key resource for standardizing procedures to realize vertical reference systems. However, the gravity databases of many countries, such as Brazil, do not contain GNSS information for all densification, and a specific transformation must be performed to determine gravity disturbances.

The gravity field is traditionally modeled using a deterministic method through Numerical Integration (NI) or stochastically using the Least Squares Collocation (LSC) method (FORBERG; TSCHERNING, 1981). In the first case, the kernel should be adequately modified, and in the second, the parameters should be consistently adjusted using a covariance model, along with noise and signal. An important consideration in geoid modeling is that, even when a consistent methodology is applied for determining geopotential values, the results may still differ. These variations arise due to differences in data quality, spatial coverage, and specific regional characteristics. In this context, Sanchez and Barzaghi (2024) emphasize the need for corrections and adjustments, including modifications to kernel functions, variations in the size of integration caps, and the application of geophysical reductions, such as global isostatic adjustment.

Despite of the classical, well-known methods for geoid modeling and physical height realization, significant discrepancies of up to 2 m exist between the systems of border countries (IHDE et al., 2017). The challenge of standardizing solutions for a global unified system has been a focus area of the Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS), whose primary objective is to monitor the Earth (PLAG; PEARLMAN, 2009). The definition begins with IAG resolution No. 1, followed by Resolution 2 for the Global Absolute Gravity Reference System (IAG, 2015). The latter is referred to as International Terrestrial Gravity Reference System (ITGRS) to avoid confusion with another acronym already in use (SÁNCHEZ et al., 2023). The general purpose is to establish a consistent physical height system equivalent to the International Terrestrial Reference System (ITRS) and the International Celestial Reference System (ICRS). In this sense, the study group of the International Height Reference System and Frame (IHRF/IHRF) recently searched for the standardization of the parameters and corrections to define compatible solutions related to the Earth's gravity field potential W_0 , using distinct approaches (SÁNCHEZ et al., 2021; WANG, 2021).

Regarding Brazil's geodetic infrastructure, although there is difficulty in establishing homogeneous measurements, the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (*Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística* - IBGE) has made significant progress in the leveling network adjustment (IBGE, 2018). Following that, the vertical component of the SGB since 2018 has been provided in terms of geopotential numbers, as recommended by IAG for IHRF. However, the altimetric and gravimetric quality and coverage remain inadequate for highly precise modeling of the gravity field quantity. In this context, states like São Paulo, which have received scientific investments, have a well-developed geodetic structure. Meanwhile, Minas Gerais, especially in the north of the state, still has regions with few geodetic information. On the other hand, over the last four years, as a result of institutional efforts, more than 600 relative gravimetric measurements have been established in the area, along with 25 absolute gravity stations.

In fact, the vertical datum unification is contingent upon the geodetic infrastructure of the countries. Given the current limitations in Brazilian data, studies can assess data deficiencies and identify potential strategies to improve geodetic information or its utilization. In this sense, another aspect of the investigation in this paper is the use of point gravity data, without gridding, for the numerical integration method. The gridding process causes signal degradation (filtering) or data alteration, but the appropriate gravity data distribution benefits the solutions when the raw point data is used directly (SAKIL et al., 2021).

In light of this, this paper aims to analyze the normal height values calculated by NI using non-gridding data and by LSC using gridding data under the IHRF conventions. The first used a particular modified kernel of Hotine, and the second used the GRAVSOF package with Fast Collocation (BOTTONI; BARZAGHI, 1993). The comparison was made using the 112 Brazilian Benchmarks (BM) of the High Precision Altimetric Network (*Rede Altimétrica de Alta Precisão* - RAAP). Additionally, the differences between the methods and normal values from RAAP are evaluated. The study area is concentrated in Southeast Brazil, specifically in the states of São Paulo and Minas Gerais.

2 METHODOLOGIES

2.1 Study area and input data

The database used in this study encompasses data from longitude (λ) 56° W to 38° W and latitude (φ) 27° S to 12° S, including regions that extend more than 2° out of São Paulo and Minas Gerais states. It belongs to the database compiled and processed by the Escola Politécnica of the University of São Paulo (EPUSP), integrating data from multiple institutions, including the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística - IBGE), CENEGEO, the National Agency of Petroleum, Natural Gas, and Biofuels (Agência Nacional do Petróleo, Gás Natural e Biocombustíveis - ANP), Petrobras, and the Mineral Resources Research Company (Companhia de Pesquisa

de Recursos Minerais – CPRM). The selection of this area is intended to enable comparative analysis between regions with gravimetric data voids, such as in Minas Gerais, and areas with adequate gravimetric coverage at a 5-minutes resolution, such as São Paulo.

For the analysis, the input data was residual gravity disturbances $\delta g^{res}(1)$, determined from terrestrial gravity disturbances δg^{terr} reduced with the Long Wavelength Component (LWC) derived from the Global Geopotential Model (GGM) XGM2019, δg_n , with the maximum degree (nmax) set to 100.

$$\delta g^{res} = \delta g^{terr} - \sum_{i=2}^n \delta g_n \quad (1)$$

where, the δg^{terr} , in terms of vector, is the difference between gravity acceleration \mathbf{g} and normal gravity $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ at the same point (P) (HEISKANEN; MORITZ, 1967, p. 2-142):

$$\delta \mathbf{g}^{terr} = \mathbf{g}_P - \boldsymbol{\gamma}_P \quad (2)$$

with, $\boldsymbol{\gamma}_P$ calculated using the upward continuation with second-order corrections based on Wenzel (1985) apud Torge and Müller (2012), using GRS80 parameters (MORITZ, 1980) and Somigliana (1929) expression.

The study was conducted using point gravity data, without gridding, for the NI approach and gridded data at a 5-minute resolution, computed using the GRAVSOFT package's SELECT program. Figure 1 shows the residual gravity disturbances in the study area, along with their statistics in Table 1. The dotted regions are the focus of a detailed analysis.

Figure 1 – Residual gravity disturbances. (1 a) gridded data and 1 b) a non gridded data (mGal).

Source: The authors (2025).

Table 1 – Residual gravity disturbances statistics (mGal).

δg^{res}	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	Minimum	Maximum	Count
non-gridding	0.50	21.13	-59.99	60.00	122321
gridding	-0.63	14.83	-60.00	59.60	41040

Source: The authors (2025).

2.2 Normal height from Numeric Integration using a modified kernel of Hotine

The numerical integration methodology requires a representative kernel to ensure the convergence of the function, minimize numerical errors, and reduce spectral leakage effects (VANICEK; FEATHERSTON, 1998). In light of this, software based on the Hotine integral, also known as the Hotine-Koch integral, with a proper modification, was developed to compute the residual disturbing potential.

The routine program presents as output the residual disturbing potential (T_{res}) given by the Expression (Exp) (3), which was determined for a set of 112 BM (HOFMANN-WELLENHOF; MORITZ, 2006, Exp 2-370).

$$T_{res} = \frac{R}{4\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi} H_l^m(\psi) \delta g_{res} \sin\psi d\psi d\alpha \quad (3)$$

where, H_l^m is Hotine's modified kernel and R is the radius of the mean sphere.

It is worth mentioning that for each BM, the gravity data points for the Hotine approach were selected from the database around a radius of approximately 200 km (~ 20000 km/nmax; Torge and Müller, 2012). The LWC of the gravity disturbances was derived from the XGM2019, nmax=100, to ensure compatibility with the spatial resolution of the selected area and the spectral decomposition as presented by Torge and Müller (2012, p. 74).

The resulting residual disturbing potential needs to be restored as:

$$T_{rest} = T_{res} + T_{GGM} \quad (4)$$

The gravity potential at point P is given by:

$$W_p = U_p + T_{rest} \quad (5)$$

with, the gravity potential of the geoid $W_0 = 62636853.4 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$, conventionally adopted (IAG, 2015) and $U_o = 62636860.85 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$, normal potential at ellipsoid from GRS80 (MORITZ, 1980).

A correction corresponding to the zero-order degree term, T_{ZEGM} , between the gravitational constant (GM) from the used GGM and GRS80 ellipsoid was computed as:

$$T_{ZEGM} = \frac{GM_{GGM} - GM_{GRS80}}{R_{mean}} \quad (6)$$

where, R_{mean} is the geocentric radial distance of the computation point.

Since the quantities were computed at zero tide (ZT), it is necessary to restore the permanent tide effect of the shape of the Earth. As presented by Makinen (2021), the correction to adopt the mean tide (MT) system is:

$$W_{ZT2MT} = 0.9722 - 2.8841 \cdot \sin^2(\varphi) - 0.0195 \cdot \sin^2(\varphi) \quad (7)$$

The correction concerning the coordinates of the BM given at tide-free should be added to obtain the potential at the mean tide = zero tide position:

$$\Delta W^{ITRF}(\varphi) = -0.5901 + 1.7475 \sin^2\varphi + 0.0273 \sin^4\varphi \quad (8)$$

The geopotential number, C_p , in the mean tide system with the expected correction is:

$$C_p = W_o - (W_p + T_{ZEGM} + W_{ZT2MT} + \Delta W^{ITRF}) \quad (9)$$

The normal height, H_n , is obtained by dividing C_p by a mean normal gravity value $\overline{\gamma}_Q$ at the telluroid surface.

$$H_n = \frac{C_p}{\overline{\gamma}_Q} \quad (10)$$

with $\overline{\gamma}_Q$ determined following Hofmann-Wellenhof and Moritz (2006, p 86):

$$\overline{\gamma}_Q = \gamma_p(\varphi) \left[1 - (1 + f + m - 2f \sin^2\varphi) \frac{h_p - \zeta_{GGM}}{a} + \left(\frac{h_p - \zeta_{GGM}}{a} \right)^2 \right] \quad (11)$$

where, γ_p is the normal gravity at the ellipsoid in the geodetic latitude φ , f is the flattening of the ellipsoid, m is a form factor, a is the semi-major axis, h_p is the geodetic height and ζ_{GGM} is the height anomaly.

2.3 Normal height from gravity potential recovery from a geoid model obtained by LSC

The LSC geoid model was calculated using the same residual gravity disturbances as those used in the NI approach, with XGM2019 nmax=100, but in a 5' mean value. The first step was determining a 5-minute grid, as the routines do not allow point data. The SELECT program in the GRAVSOFTE package was used, utilizing the mean function for the interpolation process. Then, the empirical covariance function was calculated and used to adjust the model's covariance function according to the residual gravity data. After that, with covariance matrices and adjusted function, the collocation was made, and the contribution from the LWC, in terms of geoid undulations, was added to the residual ones.

For normal height determination using the geoid model in the IHRF strategy, the gravity potential must be recovered. It is worth mentioning that the calculus starts at the geoid surface, with the geoid undulation (N_p), and ends at the physical surface with the normal height value. Thus, an upward continuation based on the Bouguer plate, consistent with the Helmert orthometric height, should be applied. In the method, the provisory gravity potential (W_{prov}) is calculated as (Sanchez et al., 2021):

$$W_{prov} = W_0 - (h_p - N_p) * \bar{g} \quad (12)$$

with, the mean gravity considering the average density of topographic mass and the topographic effects TC_p , using the following:

$$\bar{g} = g_p + 0.424 * 10^{-6} (h_p - N_p) + TC_p \quad (13)$$

Then, the gravity potential in the zero-tide system is:

$$W_{ZT} = W_{prov} + \Delta W^{ITRF} \quad (14)$$

The geopotential number in the mean tide system is determined by applying the correction from W_{ZT2MT} , Exp (8):

$$C_{MT} = W_0 - (W_{ZT} + W_{ZT2MT}) \quad (15)$$

with, the mean normal gravity at the telluroid surface given by Exp (11).

$$H_n^{LSC} = \frac{C_{MT}}{\gamma_Q} \quad (16)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To investigate solutions in regions with good gravity coverage and areas of gravimetric voids, the blocks illustrated in Fig. 1 were separated (Fig. 2 and Table 2). Additionally, high-quality BMs, part of the RAAP, were selected for comparison with the solutions. These BMs have geodetic heights determined by GNSS and normal heights determined by leveling. These latter values used the technique of spirit leveling, referenced to the Imituba datum, which is based on mean sea level.

Table 2 provides a statistical overview of the residual gravity disturbances associated with two distinct methodologies: the gridding method (LSC) and the non-gridding approach (NI). Additionally, it details the normal height difference (ΔH_n (NI-LSC)) between the LSC and NI results for specific benchmarks across different blocks. Figure 2 graphically depicts these normal height discrepancies by block, as presented in the final column of Table 2.

Table 2 – Blocks of the study area with their respective residual gravity disturbance statistics and normal height discrepancies (ΔH_n (NI-LSC)) (Grid [λ_{min} , λ_{max}] x [ϕ_{min} , ϕ_{max}]).

Statistics	δg^{res} Gridding (mGal)	δg^{res} Non-gridding (mGal)	H_n (NI-LSC) (m)
Grid [-47°, -45°] x [-17°, -15°] - Block n° 1			
Mean	-0.32	-2.84	0.00
SD	15.67	18.96	0.25
Minimum	-34.90	-34.86	-0.40
Maximum	38.80	38.77	0.36
RMS	15.67	19.18	0.25

Table 2 (cont.) – Blocks of the study area with their respective residual gravity disturbance statistics and normal height discrepancies (ΔH_n (NI-LSC)) (Grid $[\lambda_{min}, \lambda_{max}] \times [\varphi_{min}, \varphi_{max}]$).

Statistics	δg^{res} Gridding (mGal)	δg^{res} Non-gridding (mGal)	H_n (NI-LSC) (m)
Grid $[-49^\circ, -47^\circ] \times [-21^\circ, -19^\circ]$ - Block n° 2			
Mean	-0.66	-0.58	0.02
SD	18.06	20.21	0.24
Minimum	-51.90	-54.99	-0.47
Maximum	47.90	48.61	-0.38
RMS	-0.66	-0.58	0.02
Grid $[-49^\circ, -47^\circ] \times [-23^\circ, -21^\circ]$ - Block n° 3			
Mean	-4.10	-3.19	0.24
SD	10.40	10.55	0.19
Minimum	-29.70	-56.47	-0.04
Maximum	40.00	40.02	0.55
RMS	11.18	11.02	0.30
Grid $[-49^\circ, -47^\circ] \times [-25^\circ, -23^\circ]$ - Block n° 4			
Mean	-2.99	-4.88	-0.86
SD	19.06	22.52	0.21
Minimum	-58.30	-59.97	-1.06
Maximum	42.20	48.85	-0.65
RMS	19.29	23.04	0.88

Figure 2 - Blocks from the study area (Grid $[\lambda_{min}, \lambda_{max}] \times [\varphi_{min}, \varphi_{max}]$) and normal height discrepancies (ΔH_n (NI-LSC)).

Regarding the methods, the LSC method calculated the geoid based on the covariance model, data density, the variance of gravity disturbances, and the distance from the prediction point. Locations with gravimetric voids can be subject to boundary effects, resulting in distortions of the original quantities. While the NI used data around 200 km from the computation point, and only the raw data was taken into account. Thus, the results reflect the existing data. On the other hand, quantities with high residual values can receive a high weight and be inserted into the integral in a non-smooth manner.

The analysis of mean and SD (Table 2) with gridding and non-gridded data showed that the largest discrepancies in normal height between methodologies occur in areas with significant changes in gravity disturbance values, such as the Grid $[-49^\circ, -47^\circ] \times [-23^\circ, -21^\circ]$, dotted regions illustrated in Fig. 1. In the case of the grids with adequate gravimetric coverage $[-49^\circ, -47^\circ] \times [-21^\circ, -19^\circ]$ and with some gravimetric voids $[-47^\circ, -45^\circ] \times [-17^\circ, -15^\circ]$, the comparison showed that there are no significant discrepancies in the results, in terms of mean, once the gravity disturbances are smoothed (dotted regions in Fig. 1). In this way, the grid or point data can be applied without distorting the quantities. On the contrary, the cost area presents an abrupt change in gravity disturbances and height value. Since there is a gravimetric void, the results of both methodologies are prejudiced.

The calculus performed for 112 benchmarks spaced in Minas Gerais and São Paulo, comparing the normal height from LSC and NI methodologies, is presented in Table 3 and Fig. 3. The comparison of these methods with the normal height from IBGE is shown in Table 3 and Fig. 4.

Table 3 – Statistics of normal height differences between methods (m) for 112 BM.

Statistics	ΔH_n (NI-LSC)	ΔH_n (IBGE-LSC)	ΔH_n (IBGE-NI)
Mean	-0.05	0.54	0.60
Standard error	0.03	0.02	0.03
Median	-0.02	0.55	0.56
SD	0.32	0.19	0.35
Minimum	-1.06	0.07	-0.33
Maximum	0.80	1.39	1.43
Count	112	112	112

The comparison between the LSC and NI presented satisfactory results, with a mean of -0.05 m, proving the reliability of the modified Hotine kernel and the non-gridded method. However, due to the gravimetric voids, input data format, and other particularities of each approach, the discrepancies ranged from -1.06 m, affecting the standard deviation (SD) result by 0.32 m.

Figure 3 – Difference between normal height from LSC and NI in the BM.

From the RAAP perspective, the normal values (IBGE) were determined and adjusted using gravity acceleration data and spirit leveling lines that date back to the 1960s. Additionally, it's worth noting the improper placement of some BMs, such as one in the south of São Paulo state and possibly others, as revealed in the 2018 RAAP readjustment. Although these benchmarks were initially classified as high-quality, their values changed considerably after 2018 due to line issues. They were not eliminated from the network because of a lack of altimetric data for validation.

Comparing the LSC normal height values with the IBGE, there is a standard deviation of 0.19 m and a mean of 0.54 m. The NI normal height values and the IBGE ones result in a standard deviation of 0.35 m and a mean value of 0.60 m. The mean and standard deviation (SD) reflect the consistency of the solutions, which are highly related to the gravimetric and altimetric data of Southeast Brazil, as the used LWC component contributed with just the nmax equal 100.

In Fig. 4, discrepancies for the LSC (b) and NI (a) in relation IBGE normal heights can be observed through the vectors. The differences were interpolated to provide an overview. Most of the differences are positive once the IBGE RAAP realization is above W_0 surface. A notable change in behavior between LSC and NI is evident in southeast São Paulo and areas with significant changes in the residual gravity disturbance values, such as the south of São Paulo (Vale do Ribeira) and the southwest of Minas Gerais. The reason may be largely related to the heterogeneity of the input data, including both grid and non-gridded data, in the strategies used.

Figure 4 – Normal height difference vectors for 112 BM: a) NI-IBGE b) NI-LSC).

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study evaluated two distinct strategies for determining normal heights under the International Height Reference Frame (IHRF): (i) recovery of gravity potential from the geoid, computed Least Squares Collocation (LSC) with gridded data; and (ii) determination of the disturbing potential via Numerical Integration (NI) with a modified Hotine kernel applied to non-gridded terrestrial gravity data.

The comparison using 112 benchmarks from RAAP in Southeast Brazil demonstrated a mean difference of -0.05 m between the LSC and NI solutions, and a mean of 0.57 m relative to the IBGE official heights. The two methods yielded consistent results in regions characterized by smooth gravity disturbance patterns, thereby confirming the feasibility of utilizing gridded data in areas exhibiting sufficient spatial coverage. However, larger discrepancies were observed in regions with abrupt gravity changes or sparse gravimetric data, highlighting the sensitivity of the methods to data distribution and quality.

The use of a GGM truncated at degree 100 (XGM2019) proved to be compatible with the regional terrestrial gravity resolution. In the NI strategy, a 200 km radius of raw gravity data was effective for potential recovery. These results reinforce the importance of targeted densification of gravimetric observations in key areas, particularly in countries with extensive territories and uneven geodetic infrastructure.

Future developments should explore the impact of higher-resolution GGMs and denser gravity datasets, as well as the inclusion of high-resolution Digital Terrain Models to improve the gravity potential recovery through and remove-restore techniques. The integration of precise altimetric and gravimetric data remains fundamental for the realization of the IHRF in South America.

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